

Untitled form

Survey based study of Sustainable VSC (SEM analysis).

Kindly fill this this Survey form for analysis of sustainable Vaccine Supply Chain.

Rate indicator given below as per your knowledge and experience contributing to sustainable vaccine supply chain.

For example if you think EVS1 (Cold chain carbon) is contributing heavily to Sustainable VSC then rate 5 in the options.

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Not shared

AGE

- 18-30
- 31-50
- 50+

Education

- High School
- Graduation
- Higher Degree

Employment

- Employed
- Unemployed
- Students

Income

- Low
- Middle
- High

Location

- Rural
- Urban
- Semi-Urban

EVS1 (Cold Chain Carbon)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

EVS2(Renewable Energy)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

EVS3 (Waste Management Efficiency)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

EVS4 (Packaging Sustainability)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

EVS5 (Water Usage Efficiency)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

EVS6 (Chemical Management)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

EVS7 (Emission Controls in Transportation)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

EVS8 (Energy Efficient Storage Facilities)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

EVS9 (Biodiversity Impact)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

ECS1(Cost-Effectiveness)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

ECS2(Supply Chain Resilience)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

ECS3(Local Sourcing Index)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

ECS4(Investment in Sustainable Technologies)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

ECS5(Inventory Management Efficiency)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

ECS6(Market Dependency)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

ECS7(ROI for Sustainability Initiatives)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

ECS8(Funding Diversification)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

ECS9(Economic Impact on Local Communities)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

SSS1 (Immunization Coverage Rate)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

SSS2 (Healthcare Worker Training and Support)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

SSS 3(Community Engagement and Education)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

SSS 4(Equitable Vaccine Distribution)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

SSS 5(Cultural Sensitivity in Vaccine Delivery)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

SSS 6(Impact on Local Employment)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

SSS 7(Public Health Outcome Improvement)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

SSS 8 (Feedback Mechanism Effectiveness)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

SDG3 (Good Health and Well-being)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

SDG9 (Clean Water and Sanitation)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

SDG 10(Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

SDG 12(Reduced Inequalities)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

SDG 16 (Responsible Consumption and Production)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals)

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

Submit

Clear form

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